

Action Plan

Cooperation and clustering transformative change projects and initiatives

31 August 2023

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Technical References

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 PU = Public
 PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
 RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)
 CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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1 Introduction

There is growing agreement on the need for transformative change to address global challenges, such as biodiversity loss. However, there is less agreement about *what* transformative change entails and *how* it can be achieved. To address these knowledge gaps, the Horizon Europe Work Programme funded 11 Horizon Europe-funded projects with a core focus on enabling transformative change for biodiversity (Figure 1).

The European Research Executive Agency (REA) has requested that these so-called 'sister projects' include collaborative activities in their workplan to better harness the synergies and common areas of work in the contexts of transformative change for biodiversity, to maximize the impact and exploitation of results of the projects and facilitate feedback to policy. Moreover there is cooperation with other relevant EU initiatives, such as BioAgora which is setting up the Science Service for biodiversity.

BIOTraCes' partners are part of other transformative change and biodiversity conservation national and international projects and networks, as for example IPBES, IPCC, Altnet, CBD. Exchange of (new) knowledge is also taking place between these initiatives.

This report summarizes work already done and forthcoming plans by BIOTraCes on fostering collaboration and creation of synergies and cooperation with sister projects and initiatives of interest, including Horizon Europe activities such as the European Partnerships and Missions.

Figure 1: Sister projects as listed on BIOTraCes <https://www.biotraces.eu/project/#sister>

Deliverable 5.8: Action Plan for Clustering Activities

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Table 1 List of sister projects, hyperlinked to their websites, and showing the coordinator and communicator contacts

Project	Coordination	Coordination contact	Communication	Communication contact
BAMBOO	Francesca Verones	Francesca.verones@ntnu.no	Sedona Anderson	sedona.anderson@ntnu.no
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2 Action Plan for Clustering Activities

The collaborative activities with the sister projects will evolve as findings mature, and the specific engagement needs emerge. Some projects last only three years, BIOTraCes lasts four years. We will investigate how we can align timelines to maintain momentum. In addition to collaborating with the sister projects, we are in close collaboration with BioAgora, which is a flagship Horizon Europe project currently setting up the Science Service for biodiversity. Members of BIOTraCes are specifically involved in setting up a framework to examine the transformative potential of science-policy interfaces. The work in BIOTraCes provides valuable insights.

To synergise our work and maximise inter-project impact and exploitation of results, BIOTraCes commits to three planned activities with relevant sister project(s) (Figure 2). A further activity of *ad hoc* online meetings between BIOTraCes and other sister projects to signify our commitment to collaborating with sister projects where we identify an opportunities or needs. For example, in a case study or conference or policy event where collaboration can mutually enhance advancing knowledge or implementation.

Each of these activities is explained in further detail below.

QUARTER	YEAR 1				YEAR 2				YEAR 3				YEAR 4			
	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4
Maintain Working Group on "Values, Norms and Justice"	x		x		x		x		x		x		x		x	
Annual events with sister project(s)				x				x				x				x
Case Study Reflections across sister project(s)								x							x	
Online ad hoc meetings with sister project(s)	when needed															

Figure 2: Timeline of collaborative activities with sister projects

2.1 Maintain Working Group 3 on 'Values, Norms and Justice'

Collaboration across the sister projects is encouraged through the establishment of three working groups:

Working group 1. Biodiversity Nexus, towards a nature positive society

Working Group 2. Production, consumption and global trade, including Business and Financing

Working Group 3: Values, norms, justice and societal agency to accelerate transformations for biodiversity

BIOTraCes and PLANET4B currently co-lead the Working Group 3 on Values, Norms and Justice. A living 'Action Plan' document is co-created with partner input from projects within WG3 (Annex 1). This document sets out an initial 6 month plan. Currently, there are 4 general activities, which will be updated upon a meeting of BIOTraCes, PLANET4B, TC4BE, TRANSPATH at the first annual event, planned 24-27 October 2023:

- Mapping project synergies in a shared document
- Meetings to coordinate activities (online and in person)
- Learning and knowledge exchange that deep-dive into particular topics
- Evolving perspectives on the social justice components of our sister projects

2.2 Annual events with sister projects

During the first cluster meeting in Brussels, it became clear that several of the WG3 members were going to be represented at the 2023 Earth Systems Governance conference, October 2023, including members from BIOTraCes, PLANET4B, TC4BE and TRANSPATH.

We have agreed to support and contribute to each other's approved sessions, for example by being a discussant in a panel. In particular, there is one interactive session, which we will try to design around, eliciting reflections from participating sister projects on "Value-oriented transformative governance for biodiversity".

And we will arrange a side HYBRID meeting during the conference to discuss:

- Identifying a potential joint session at a 2024 conference
- Identifying a topic for an online learning event between the sister projects
- Discussing what format the case study reflections session could take
- Consideration of a joint PhD webinar

2.3 Case study reflections across sister 'projects' 2024/ 2025

This is a potential joint activity that BIOTraCes, TC4BE and PLANET4B have identified for some time towards the second half of 2024 or early 2025. We would map the joint spread of case studies in the sister projects and hear about them from each other. We are likely to focus on one or both of the following issues: setting up case studies for transformative research; mapping promising leverage points and levers across case studies (similarities and differences). This will be further discussed at the 2023 Earth Systems Governance conference.

3 Joint activities completed

3.1 Working Group 3 on "Values, Norms and Justice"

During the first six months, BIOTraCes worked with PLANET4B to co-develop a first draft of the Working Group 3 Action Plan. The continuation and co-leadership will be discussed at the 2023 Earth Systems Governance conference. BIOTraCes are happy to continue to play a strong role in ensuring its continuity, and have been involved in several coordination meetings as described in section 3.2.

3.2 Online meetings with sister project(s) and other initiatives

A joint workshop was organised on the 29th of June between project representatives of BIOTraCes, BIOTRAILS, BioAgora, TRANSPATH and PLANET4B to discuss potential joint actions. The activities laid out in Working Group 3 Annex 1 capture and build on what was agreed at this workshop.

3.3 Participation in umbrella website for communication

BIOTraCes is participating with BioValue, TRANSPATH and other projects to form umbrella websites of communicators lists and stakeholder lists, and repost each other's social media posts.

Annex 1: Action plan for Working Group 3 on values, norms and justice, submitted by co-lead PLANET4B